

Grey Wolf Optimizer Based Optimal Location and Sizing of Capacitor in Power System

(Pengoptimum Serigala Kelabu Berdasarkan Penempatan dan Ukuran Optimum Kapasitor dalam Sistem Kuasa)

*Nurul Aini Endri, Nor Azwan Mohamed Kamari

*Electrical and Electronics Engineering Program,
Faculty of Engineering & Built Environment, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia*

ABSTRACT

Capacitor has been introduced in the bus system for improvement of power factor, reducing reactive power losses and to overcome unstable voltage. In this paper an index and algorithm are applied with power flow to simulate the best location of capacitor in IEEE bus system considering the effect of capacitor to system voltage stability referred as Fast Voltage Stability Index (FVSI) and Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO). The proposed index and algorithm are tested in 6-bus and 30-bus system using MATLAB. This index is used to measure each line in bus system and to find the most sensitive bus of both test bus system. The line that has highest FVSI value indicates that the line is most sensitive and bus that connected to the line is the optimal location of capacitor to be installed. Capacitor is then placed in the bus that connected to the sensitive line with given capacitor range. GWO optimize the capacitor value to be installed in the bus by considering minimum FVSI value observed. Both FVSI value before and after installing the capacitor is compared to show which bus responds to the installed capacitor the most. Overall proposed methods are simple and take less time to observe the results.

ABSTRAK

Kapasitor telah diperkenalkan di dalam sistem bus untuk penambahbaikan faktor kuasa, mengurangkan kehilangan kuasa reaktif dan untuk mengatasi voltan yang tidak stabil. Dalam projek ini indeks dan algoritma digunakan dengan aliran kuasa untuk mensimulasikan lokasi kapasitor yang terbaik dalam sistem bus IEEE dengan mengambil kira kesan kapasitor kepada kestabilan voltan sistem dirujuk sebagai Indeks Kestabilan Voltan Pantas (FVSI) dan Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO). Indeks dan algoritma yang dicadangkan diuji dalam sistem 6-bus dan 30-bus menggunakan MATLAB. Indeks ini digunakan untuk mengukur setiap garis dalam sistem bus dan untuk mencari bus yang paling sensitif bagi kedua-dua sistem bus yang diuji. Garis yang mempunyai nilai FVSI tertinggi menunjukkan bahawa garis tersebut yang paling sensitif dan bus yang menyambung ke garisan tersebut adalah lokasi yang paling optimum untuk pemasangan kapasitor. Kapasitor dipasang pada bus sensitif dalam julat kapasitor yang diberikan. GWO mengoptimumkan nilai kapasitor yang akan dipasang di dalam bus dengan mempertimbangkan nilai minimum FVSI yang diperhatikan. Kedua-dua nilai FVSI sebelum dan sesudah memasang kapasitor dibandingkan untuk memerhatikan respon terhadap bus mana yang menunjukkan respon yang paling banyak kepada pemasangan kapasitor. Keseluruhan kaedah yang dicadangkan adalah mudah dan mengambil masa yang untuk melihat hasilnya.

INTRODUCTION

The demand for power transmission network is growing due to the rapid development to meet the needs of consumers (Modi et al. 2007). Therefore, the existing power system need to be improved to produce high electric efficiency. The electric efficiency can be achieved by achieve voltage stability. The search of mathematical calculation and

analysis of power loss in the system as well as finding the appropriate method to achieve voltage stability is needed.

Generally power losses due to reactive losses can be prevented by various method like improvement of power factor, placement of FACT device and also capacitor placement. In this paper capacitor bank is used and placed in IEEE bus system. The optimal location and sizing of capacitor

bank is considered to increase dynamic system and system capabilities which in turn increase electric efficiency.

In the past, various of optimizing methods have been introduced. (Shuaib et al. 2015) proposed two method to optimize the location of capacitor in radial distribution system. Sensitivity analysis is used to find out maximum location that influenced active power losses of the system regarding the node reactive and to calculate the Loss Sensitivity Factor (LSF). While, Gravitational Search Algorithm (GSA) is used to calculate the optimum capacitor size based on voltage profile minimum cost. (Devabalaji et al. 2015) also done almost same research with (Shuaib et al. 2015) but replacing GSA with Bacterial Foraging Algorithm (BFA).

On the other hand, (Zeinalzadeh et al. 2015) calculate the optimal placement and sizing of distributed generations (DG) and shunt capacitor banks (SCBs). They used multi objective particle swarm optimization (MOPSO) that consider the load uncertainty in distribution systems. (Kavousi Fard & Niknam 2014) proposed an optimization system based on firefly algorithm (FA) by taking into account both constant and dynamic peak load models. (Mishra et al. 2017) applied load flow in MATLAB to determine optimal placement of Y-Δ connected capacitor bank to minimize both active and reactive power loss in IEEE five-bus power system.

A hybrid method which combined both Genetic Algorithm (GA) and Imperialist Competitive Algorithm (ICA) to determine optimal location and size of DGs and SCBs has been proposed by (Moradi et al. 2014). In this project, they implemented on IEEE thirty-three-bus and sixty-nine-bus radial distribution systems. (Tamilselvan et al. 2015) presents the optimal capacitor placement and sizing in Radial Distribution System (RDS) using Clonal Selection Algorithmic (CSA) method to minimize cost of energy and power loss, simultaneously. All of the optimizing methods have achieved the inspiring results in fathoming the optimal location of capacitor in both IEEE and radial distribution system. In spite of those achievements, they also have a lack in time solving of capacitor compared to grey wolf which has simple algorithm.

In this project, Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO) has been proposed to fathom the optimal placement and sizing of capacitor in IEEE bus system. At first, FVSI indices is used to measure each line in the bus system to find the most unstable line in the bus. Then, the bus that connected to the line is placed with capacitor. GWO is applied to calculate the location and tuned the value of capacitor to be placed in the unstable bus. GWO algorithm is one of the newest metaheuristic swarm intelligence method that focused on hierarchy of leadership and preying mechanism of grey wolf

nature compared to other previously developed optimization techniques. It has a special capability to strike the right balance between exploration and exploitation during the search of prey which leads to favorable convergence.

METHODOLOGY

In this paper, Fast Voltage Stability Index (FVSI) and Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO) are proposed to calculate the optimal capacitor location and size in bus system. This test is done in IEEE six-bus and thirty-bus system using MATLAB software, as shown in Figure 1 and 2, respectively.

FIGURE 1. Six-bus system

FIGURE 2. Thirty-bus system

Fast Voltage Stability Index (FVSI)

FVSI index is a line-based voltage stability index where it could decide the voltage stability condition of all line in power system (Mathew et al. 2015). In this paper FVSI is proposed to calculate the optimal location and size of capacitor in bus system. The FVSI value is measured in each line of the bus

system and sort from the lowest to highest value. The line i th- j th that has highest FVSI value will be placed with capacitor either at i th or j th bus.

$$FVSI_{ij} = \frac{4Z_{ij}^2 Q_j}{V_i^2 X_{ij}} \quad (1)$$

Z_{ij} : line impedance

X_{ij} : line reactance

V_i : voltage at the sending end

Q_j : reactive power at the receiving end

In measuring the line, the value of FVSI should be less than 1 to achieve stable system. If the value of FVSI is closed to 1, it shows that the line has reached voltage instability limit that leads to sudden voltage drop and next cause the system instability.

Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO)

Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO) has been proposed by Mirjalili in 2014. It is a meta-heuristic optimization algorithm that inspired by animal behavior (Kamboj et al. 2015). It mimics the hierarchy of leadership and preying mechanism of grey wolf in nature. In this algorithm, four categories of Grey Wolves alpha, beta, delta and omega are applied for simulating hierarchy of leadership as shown in Figure 3.

FIGURE 3. Hierarchy of grey wolf

The main steps in preying mechanism of grey wolf are searching, hunting, encircling and attacking prey. The flow chart of GWO is shown in Figure 4.

1. The encircling of prey

Grey wolf starts the preying mechanism by encircle the prey. The encircling approach is determined as follows.

$$D = |C \cdot X_p(k) - X(k)| \quad (2)$$

$$X(k + 1) = X_p(k) - A \cdot D \quad (3)$$

where k is current iteration, X_p and X are the position vector of the prey and a grey wolf, respectively. Both A and C are the coefficient vectors.

FIGURE 4. Flow chart of GWO

The value of A and C can be determined by:

$$A = 2a \cdot r_1 - a \tag{4}$$

$$C = 2 \cdot r_2 \tag{5}$$

where, both r_1 and r_2 are random numbers between $[0,2]$. Element a is set to decrease gradually from 2 to 0 throughout the simulation process.

2. The hunting of prey

From the initial calculation of all wolves' position, top three best location of the wolf leaders can be indicated as alpha (best candidate solution), beta (second best candidate solution) and delta (third best candidate solution). For the other search wolf, they need to update their position based on the average of their top three best wolf leaders. The calculation of updating other wolves can be shown as the followings:

$$D_\alpha = |C_1 \cdot X_\alpha - X| \tag{6}$$

$$D_\beta = |C_2 \cdot X_\beta - X| \tag{7}$$

$$D_\delta = |C_3 \cdot X_\delta - X| \tag{8}$$

$$X_1 = |X_\alpha - A_1 \cdot (D_\alpha)| \tag{9}$$

$$X_2 = |X_\beta - A_2 \cdot (D_\beta)| \tag{10}$$

$$X_3 = |X_\delta - A_3 \cdot (D_\delta)| \tag{11}$$

$$X(k + 1) = \frac{X_1 + X_2 + X_3}{3} \tag{12}$$

3. The attacking of prey (exploitation):

Here the value of A is set to decrease gradually from 2 to 0 throughout the simulation, while search wolves of next location will be in any place. When the value of A is in range of $[-1,1]$, grey wolf attacks the prey.

4. The searching for prey (exploration):

Here search agent is diverged from the prey by employed A with random value bigger than 1 or less than -1. Thus, GWO could explore globally

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this paper, the optimal location and size of capacitor is simulated in MATLAB. IEEE six-bus and thirty-bus system is selected as test system. Each line of bus system is measured using FVSI index using equation (1) by considering no capacitor placement at first and then compared with the FVSI value after capacitor is placed.

Table 1 tabulates the result of location and size of capacitor for both IEEE six-bus and thirty-bus systems. From the result of IEEE six-bus system, the highest FVSI value is at line 4. This

means that line 4 is the most sensitive line in the test system. Thus, the optimum location of capacitor is at bus connected to the line which is bus 5. For IEEE thirty-bus system, the highest value of FVSI is at line 15. Thus, the optimum location of capacitor is at bus connected to the line which is bus 4. The optimum capacitor value injected for six-bus system is 0.171 Mvar. While thirty-bus system, the optimum capacitor value is 3.8953 Mvar.

TABLE 1. Application of FVSI index in bus system

IEEE Bus System	Sensitive line and bus	Highest FVSI value	Optimal capacitor Size (Mvar)
Six	4 (bus 5)	0.2403	0.171
Thirty	15 (bus 4)	0.2035	3.8953

TABLE 2. FVSI value for 6 bus system

Line (bus to bus)	Without capacitor	With capacitor
1 – 6	0.0075	0.0064
1 – 4	0.0454	0.0451
4 – 6	0.0598	0.0589
6 – 5	0.2403	0.2367
2 – 5	0.2155	0.2113
2 – 3	0.1700	0.1674
4 – 3	0.1168	0.1164

Table 2 tabulates the FVSI value for each line in IEEE six-bus system, with and without capacitor. From the result, it clearly shows that lines related to Bus 5, which are Line 6-5 and 2-5, have higher FVSI value compared to other lines. After injecting capacitor to Bus 5, FVSI value for both lines reduce dramatically.

FIGURE 5. Six-bus system ($Q_c=0.171$ Mvar at bus 5)

Figure 5 shows the correlation of each lines in IEEE six-bus system, when with and without capacitor. It is clearly showing that Line 4 has the highest FVSI. After capacitor placement, the FVSI value has reduced.

FIGURE 6. Thirty-bus system ($Q_c=3.8953\text{Mvar}$ at bus 4)

Figure 6 shows the correlation of each lines in IEEE thirty-bus system, when with and without capacitor. The highest value of FVSI is Line 15. After capacitor placement, the FVSI value at Line 15 has reduced drastically.

TABLE 3. FVSI value for 30 bus system

Line (bus to bus)	Without capacitor	With capacitor
1 – 2	0.0809	0.0808
1 – 3	0.0330	0.0286
2 - 4	0.0094	0.0039
3 – 4	0.0091	0.0080
2 – 5	0.0663	0.0662
2 – 6	0.0390	0.0369
4 – 6	0.0335	0.0298
5 – 7	0.0587	0.0574
6 – 7	0.0076	0.0067
6 – 8	0.0065	0.0043
6 – 9	0.1656	0.1647
6 – 10	0.1450	0.1445
9 – 11	0.1214	0.1200
9 – 10	0.0237	0.0234
4 – 12	0.2035	0.1994
12 – 13	0.0522	0.0503
12 – 14	0.0258	0.0258
12 – 15	0.0383	0.0383
12 – 16	0.0285	0.0283
14 – 15	0.0109	0.0112

Table 3 tabulates the FVSI value for each line in IEEE thirty-bus system, with and without capacitor. From the result, it shows that line 4-12 has highest FVSI value, 0.2035 compared to other lines. After injecting capacitor to Bus 4, FVSI value for that line reduce to 0.1994.

From the simulated results, it can be concluded that by installing the capacitor to the bus will decrease the FVSI value which means that the voltage stability of the system has been improved.

CONCLUSION

This paper presented Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO) method as an optimization technique to fathom the optimal location and sizing of capacitor to improve voltage stability in power system. It has been tested using IEEE six-bus and thirty-bus systems in MATLAB environment. The FVSI index was applied to find the most unstable voltage in the bus for capacitor placement. Then, GWO is used to determine the size of capacitor at the selected bus. The results showed that by installing capacitor at the bus, the FVSI value has decreased. Therefore, it can be justified that GWO is capable to optimize location and value of capacitor that injected at the bus and then increase the voltage stability of power system.

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*Nurul Aini binti Endri,
Electrical and Electronics Engineering Program,
Faculty of Engineering and Built Environment,
Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia (UKM), Bangi,
Malaysia

*Corresponding author; email:
nurulaini@siswa.ukm.edu.my